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Auteur Cinema of Pakistan: Filmmakers' Perspective on Sociocultural Complexities of Pakistan

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Abstract

This study examines the complexities of the social problems of Pakistan explained by Pakistani independent filmmakers in their films. Four independent films that were produced in the past two decades by two Pakistani filmmakers, Shoaib Mansoor and Sabiha Sumar, were analyzed for their discourses. The findings show that the directors articulated the dynamics of women's oppression and the sociopolitical climate of Pakistan by using their own distinctive approaches. The films centered mainly on a critique of Islamic fundamentalism and patriarchal culture as the main driving forces of social problems that determine women's status in Pakistan. In the process of articulating the complexity of social problems, it was evident that Mansoor represented the problem in a cultural context by placing certain ethnic identities as the causal agents while Sumar framed the problem to be driven mainly by certain ideological forces. Furthermore, Mansoor's movies portrayed a more optimistic viewpoint, suggesting that women's rights could be advanced through current legal measures and economic changes within the country. Sumar's films, on the other hand, were more realistic, representing the prevailing status of women in Pakistani society. Her films suggest that women's empowerment in the existing social system and state institutions is improbable.

Keywords: *Auteur Cinema, Pakistani Filmmakers, Pakistan Media, Patriarchy, Media Discourse*

Introduction

Popular culture has conveyed and transformed the perception of social identities of groups and cultures through their unique presentation. The present research examines the views of filmmakers Shoaib Mansoor and Sabiha Sumar, a male and female respectively, on the complexities of social problems in Pakistani society. This is done by analyzing the narrative in four of their independent Pakistani films. The four films analyzed in the study are *Khuda Kay Liye (In the Name of God)* directed by Shoaib Mansoor in 2007, *Bol (Speak)* directed by Mansoor in 2011, *Khamosh Pani (Silent Waters)* directed by Sabiha Sumar in 2003, and *Good Morning Karachi* directed by Sumar in 2013. This research endeavors to comprehend the strategies employed by the directors in portraying discourses relating to women in relation to culture and religion, and how such discourses influence the position of women and the contemporary social difficulties they face in Pakistan. It also examines their pursuits for empowerment and the various opportunities available to them to overcome these challenges.

The influence of popular media in shaping people's perceived identities, socialization, and life choices guides the inquisitiveness about the way these filmmakers portrayed the conflicts concerning gender in relation to the religion

and culture of Pakistan. Popular media significantly influences how people consume these representations in addition to producing images and representations that commodify culture (Trier-Bieniek, 2015). The understudied films are the examples of popular media that have helped shape the discourse about the status of women in relation to religion and culture in Pakistan. The literature about auteur theory of cinema in general, and Pakistani cinema in particular, came under limited investigations. Rehman (2016) undertook a detailed analysis of independent films from Pakistan for their intersection of gender, religion, and culture. The current study extends the extant literature on Pakistani cinema to the sociocultural dynamics of Pakistan constructed by Pakistani filmmakers in their films.

Filmmakers in Pakistan frequently highlight the issues of women's oppression in their films. In 2003, *Silent Waters* was directed by Sabiha Sumar in Pakistan but screened mainly outside Pakistan. *Silent Waters* addressed the abductions of women, honor killings, and the Islamization of Pakistan by the former President of Pakistan Zia-ul-Haq. Sumar released another film *Good Morning Karachi* in 2013. The film portrayed a woman's struggle to pursue a fashion industry career as a model in a male-dominated Pakistani society.

In 2007, Shoaib Mansoor produced an independent film in Pakistani, *In the Name of God*, whose main theme was the practice of forced marriage in Pakistan. The film revolves around a woman's struggle against patriarchal cultural practices of forced marriages and religious radicalism in Pakistani society. *Speak* was Mansoor's other film produced in 2011 and was based on women's status in a patriarchal family system and their struggles against such a system. The film portrayed a patriarchal and misogynist father controlling his wife and daughters' education, health, welfare, and financial independence through his fanatical extreme religious attitude and behavior.

Based on their directorship, the imprint of Sabiha Sumar and Shoaib Mansoor on their films is important to examine. Using auteur theory, the current study examines the roles of these directors in framing the status of women in relation to the religion and culture of Pakistan are analyzed. Additionally, the study also explores the ideological inferences of the discourses of these films in offering pathways for the advancement and empowerment of women.

Theoretical Framework

Narrative Analysis

The narrative quality of a text emerges when it is carefully chosen, structured in a specific manner, and linked together coherently to impart significance to the reader (Riessman, 2005). Riessman described the analysis of narratives within the realm of human sciences to highlight the various methods that can be applied to texts that take on a narrative form. In the field of

sociolinguistics, according to Riessman, a narrative can refer to a concise tale that features a character, a setting, and a sequence of events.

Riessman (2005), through his narrative model, proposed four distinct analytical perspectives for the analysis of a narration. The first method within the model is thematic analysis, which concentrates on identifying the themes and content of the narration, rather than its style or delivery. This approach is utilized in cases where linguistic intricacies and subtleties are not the focus of the inquiry and the goal is to theorize various scenarios. Interactional analysis, according to Riessman, is the second method that concentrates on the interaction and exchange between the person listening and the person narrating the story. This approach is typically employed in situations such as interviews or other forms of communication where there is an exchange of information between the person sharing the story and the person receiving it. The third method is performance analysis, which involves examining the characters and their associated identities during the act of narration and taking into account the interactional aspect of the performance including the response of the audience. The fourth and final approach is structural analysis, which aims to examine the techniques and methods used to narrate a story. This method looks into all the narrative elements that make up a story, with close scrutiny of the language used being a central part of the analysis. In the current study, the chosen approach is structural analysis, as the objective is to investigate the manner in which the stories are communicated through their narrative components such as plot, characterization, dialogue, and visuals.

Huisman and his coauthors (2005) described the plot as the creative art of making choices, combining elements, exaggerating or downplaying certain aspects, distorting information, leaving things out, speeding up or slowing down the pace, and implying certain ideas to make a basic story more engaging and captivating for a specific audience. Plot is the decision of a director to arrange the elements of a story in his/her own unique way that follows causal reasoning. Margolin (1986) defines a character as a human or human-like entity that embodies the attribution of mental state to a participant within the story. To understand the structure of a story, Stokes (2012) proposed a typological approach that includes genre studies, star studies, and auteur studies. The typological approach used in the current study is the auteur study, which refers to a director's influence on the form, style, and meaning formation in their films.

The Auteur Theory

The Auteur Theory of Cinema highlights the director's role as the primary driving force behind the creation of a film. However, some critics pointed out that the auteur theory tends to elevate certain directors above others (Allen & Lincoln, 2004). The origin of the auteur theory can be traced back to France, where Francois Truffaut published an article on the subject in the French film magazine *Cahiers du Cinema* in the 1950s. It later spread to England as well as to the United States (Staples, 1966). According to Staples, Truffaut's article was a critique of the

commercial and conventional screenwriters of French films and was not meant to establish a critical framework. Staples also claimed that the development of the auteur theory was largely influenced by the work of Andre Bazin, who served as a model for evaluating the performing arts for its visual and textual elements.

Sarris (2004) advanced the auteur theory further and asserted that technical proficiency is the foundational principle of the theory. The second aspect of the theory, according to Sarris (2004), is the identifiable personality of the director that shapes the plot of the film. According to Giannetti (2014), the style and tone of the film should reflect the director's perspective and feelings. Sarris (2004) suggested that American directors are more expressive than their foreign counterparts when it comes to conveying their personal style through visual elements of the film instead of relying on literary techniques. The third and final premise of the theory is the interior meaning. Interior meaning refers to the director's representation and interpretation of events in the film based on their personal beliefs, values, and experiences. According to Sarris, the three premises of the auteur theory can be visualized as three concentric circles, with technique as the outer circle, personal style as the middle circle, and interior meaning as the inner circle. The director's role, therefore, can be considered as a technician, stylist, and auteur based on the three premises of the auteur theory. By examining the inner circle, this study aims to uncover the unique and distinct style of the director and how it influences the story being told. This means that the focus is on how the director's personal beliefs and values shape the narrative and how these elements can be seen in the story and visual representation.

A Brief Biography of the Directors of the Films

The aim of this study is to understand the directors' personal style and the meaning they convey through their films. To achieve this goal, the films of these directors are analyzed using the framework of auteur theory and the examination of their personal and professional histories. Through this approach, the study seeks to contribute to the understanding of the directors' personal vision and the ways in which they use their films to communicate their ideas, values, and beliefs to the audience. By examining the work of both male and female directors, this study aims to provide a nuanced understanding of the auteurs' reflections on these important themes and shed light on any gender-based differences in their perspectives. To contextualize the two directors (Shoaib Mansoor and Sabiha Sumar) featured in the analysis, the professional and production histories of Shoaib Mansoor and Sabiha Sumar are important to understand in order to examine the potential impact of their personal lives and professional history on the discourses of the films of this study.

Shoaib Mansoor

Shoaib Mansoor is a multi-faceted creative, with expertise in independent filmmaking, direction, production, and music composition. Mansoor gained

popularity as a musician with the debut of music band Vital Signs in the 1980s and later transitioned into the drama and film industry where he has directed and produced several critically acclaimed films and dramas. Mansoor was the director of well-received action and thriller dramas, *Alpha*, *Bravo*, *Charlie* and *Sunehray Din* which focused on the domestic and occupational lives of the Pakistan army. The productions were undertaken by the Inter-Service Public Relations of Pakistan (ISPR). Two recent independent films of Mansoor are *In the Name of God* and *Speak*. According to Mansoor, the target audience for his films is the Muslim population in Pakistan and India (as stated in a 2008 interview). *In the Name of God* received special authorization for screening from former President of Pakistan, Pervez Musharraf.

The central themes of both of his films *Speak* and *In the Name of God* revolve around patriarchal norms and religious radicalism. Mansoor has been honored with a Lifetime Achievement Award from the state-run television service Pakistan Television, and a Sitara-e-Imtiaz, which is the highest civilian award presented by the Government of Pakistan to recognize individuals who have made significant contributions in various fields such as arts, sports, science, literature, social services, and politics. The Government of Pakistan also awarded him with the Pride of Performance award. His film *In the Name of God* was honored at the Cairo International Film Festival and received a Silver Pyramid Award. Additionally, it received the Best Film Award from Roberto Rossellini. *Speak* was nominated for the Best Feature Film category at the Asia Pacific Screen Awards. It received several awards including the Best Film Award at the Lux Style and the London Asian Film Festival, and the Best Hindi Film Award at the IRDS Film Festival.

Sabiha Sumar

Sabiha Sumar was born in Karachi – the largest city of Pakistan in 1961. She is an independent filmmaker of Pakistan and the founder of a privately-owned film production company Vidhi Film. Sumar's father was involved in both business and politics as reported by Ahmad and Anjum (2014). Sumar received her education at Sarah Lawrence College in New York, where she studied filmmaking and political science, and then went to Cambridge University to study history and political thought. Sumar has produced various documentaries, mainly around the topics of religious extremism and women's repression. *Who Will Cast the First Stone* was her first documentary that shed light on the stories of three women who were incarcerated under the Islamic law in Pakistan. The documentary received recognition and received a Golden Gate Award in 1998 at the San Francisco Film Festival. Sumar made her debut in drama films with *Silent Waters*, which was released in 2003. The film was well-received and won the Golden Leopard Award at the Locarno International Film Festival in the same year.

According to an interview with Ahmad and Anjum in 2014, Sabiha Sumar stated that the origin of *Silent Waters* was a documentary for one of her research projects, which was funded and focused on the topic of the abductions of women during the 1947 partition of India. Later on, Sumar expanded the scope of the film beyond just the historical events by also addressing the contemporary issues of

violence and religious intolerance. In the film, Sumar connected the kidnapping of women during the division of India in 1947 to the Islamization process of Zia in 1979 and the 2002 presidential referendum under Pervez Musharraf. While talking about the impact of Zia's Islamization policies, Sumar argued that those policies had a wider impact on people's lives that went beyond just TV and cinema as they led to self-censorship in homes and society (Ahmad & Anjum, 2014). She mentioned that the target audience of her film *Silent Waters* was primarily Pakistanis. She believed that the film's themes of violence and religious intolerance were relevant to the prevailing social and political situation in Pakistan and that it would resonate with her Pakistani audience.

Present Study

This study uses auteur theory and narrative analysis to understand the representation of sociocultural complexities in Pakistan in the films of two filmmakers Sabiha Sumar and Shoaib Mansoor. The auteur theory suggests that the director of a film is the "author" of the work and that their personal vision and style can be seen in the film. The study uses this theory to examine how the directors of *In the Name of God*, *Silent Waters*, *Good Morning Karachi*, and *Speak* have imprinted their personal perspectives and views on the sociocultural complexities of Pakistan in their films.

By conducting a narrative analysis of the plots, dialogues, and characters in these films, the study aims to understand how the filmmakers have represented the dynamics of gender and religious identities in Pakistan and how they have depicted the sociocultural complexities of the country. The results of this study can provide valuable insights into the filmmakers' perspectives and the ways in which these perspectives are reflected in their films. It can provide a deeper understanding of the representation of sociocultural complexities in Pakistani films and the ways in which filmmakers use their films to address these complexities. In addition, it fundamentally underscores the overarching framework that governs the process of meaning and identity formation within the realm of cinematic craftsmanship.

Method and Findings

The films were chosen based on their relevance to the research questions and their representation of the themes of gender, cultural, and religious ideologies. The study aimed to examine the ways in which Mansoor and Sumar represented these themes in their films and to identify any patterns or similarities in their representations. By analyzing the films, the study aimed to shed light on the perspectives of these two directors on the issues surrounding women's rights and empowerment. It should be noted that the characters in the understudied films speak Urdu and Punjabi languages – the two most commonly spoken languages in Pakistan. The dialogues were translated into the English language for examination and analysis. The translation was thoroughly reviewed by two Ph.D. scholars who

were fluent in Punjabi and Urdu. The films were watched three times. After an initial viewing, the plot was established based on the narrative of the film. During the second viewing, the characters were analyzed for their gender, religious, and cultural identities, and their connection to the protagonist and antagonist characters was established. On the third viewing, the dialogues were analyzed for their themes and interior meanings. The following findings were reported on the basis of narrative analysis:

Causal Agents of Women's Suppression: Religion or Culture?

The detailed examination of the films showed that Shoaib Mansoor attributed the oppression of women to misinterpretations of Islam in his films, whereas Sabiha Sumar attributed it to religion itself in her films. According to Mansoor's films, women's oppression is the result of the misapplication of religion by patriarchal forces, rather than by religion itself. For instance, the characters of Hussain (Humayun Kazmi) and Mansoor (Shaan Shahid) in *In the Name of God* clarify the distinction between cultural and religious influences by separating the two. Mansoor, who was portrayed as having moderate religious beliefs, tells Janie (Austin Marie Sayre) that his hesitation in marrying her is due to their cultural differences rather than their religious ones. Contrarily, Hussain, who is not depicted as being religious, utilized religion as a means of exerting power over Mary and forcing her into marriage.

On the other hand, Sumar portrayed religion as the primary oppressor of women, lacking any nuance regarding alternative interpretations of Islam. This is evident in *Silent Waters* where she presented Islam as a political influence to subjugate women. Similarly, in *Good Morning Karachi*, mullahs (religious clerics) were spotted vandalizing the advertisement billboards containing women's images by calling them obscene.

Generalization of Broader Social Problems to Women

Mansoor in his films addressed problems that are specific to women and are common among wider sectors of the woman population. On the other hand, Sumar tackled a wide range of issues including those specific to a particular gender, those that affect all genders, and uncommon situations that are not frequently experienced by the majority of women. Mansoor shed light on the problem of forced marriages, where the conservative societal norm is to disregard the agreement of women in matrimony. In *Speak*, he brought attention to misogyny and birth control, two issues that have a direct impact on women. For instance, many uneducated individuals in Pakistan believe that birth control is a religious transgression and that they should rely on God to provide for them. This way of thinking results in large families, poor health outcomes for mothers and children, and limited resources to support one's family.

Conversely, Sumar tackled some issues that are specific to a certain gender and others that are gender-neutral and/or less prevalent among most women. In *Silent Waters*, for example, Sumar depicted a scenario where a woman was asked to

affirm her Islamic faith. The declaration of faith is not a widely occurring practice in Pakistan (as there are few, if any, documented instances of such declarations in Pakistan) and cannot be solely associated with women. Men are more prone to making such affirmations as a result of the way they are socialized in society. Sumar also addressed some women-specific issues such as the honor killing of women. For instance, in *Silent Waters*, a Sikh father took the lives of his wife and daughter in the name of honor during the 1947 partition of India. In *Good Morning Karachi*, she brought attention to the dangers faced by a female model from Islamic extremists. Due to the patriarchal nature of Pakistani society, dress codes and modesty are mostly expected from women, and for women, fashion modeling is considered an immodest profession. That being said, the film's message, as expressed by Sumar, implies that social conservatism and religious extremism are dangers that only women face, although these issues can also affect men.

Directors' Ethnic Profiling of Characters

Mansoor's films ethnically profiled people by suggesting that some ethnic groups have higher instances of social conservatism and misogyny than others. Likewise, Mansoor's films imply that the misapplication of Islam is predominantly an issue within certain ethnic groups. Mansoor portrayed Punjabi characters and culture in a more positive light. For example, *In the Name of God* depicted all the Pashtun-ethnic people as being misogynist, patriarchal, and radical while Punjabi-ethnic people as liberal and more open-minded. The film mainly shows the city of Lahore – a predominantly Punjabi-ethnic city. In the film, Sarmad (Fawad Khan), a Punjabi ethnic man from Lahore, was radicalized by Pashtuns. He was shown remorseful for his radical and misogynist behavior at the end of the film and was shown to be misguided by a Pashtun radical man. In the film, the Punjabi character Hussain expressed remorse for compelling his daughter to marry Sarmad. However, throughout the film, the Pashtun characters were portrayed as both radical and misogynistic. In *Speak*, he linked the misogynistic perspective with the character of Hakim (Manzar Sehbai), who was of Indian ethnicity. On the other hand, Punjabi-ethnic Akhtar Hossain (Irfan Khoosat) was shown as socially liberal and women-friendly in the same film.

Sumar's films addressed the broader societal issue of patriarchy and misogyny and linked those issues to religious beliefs and practices rather than attributing them to any specific cultural or ethnic group. This approach allows for a more comprehensive and nuanced examination of the root causes of gender-based oppression. Both of her films did not highlight any specific cultural or ethnic group as being particularly patriarchal or misogynistic. In the film *Silent Waters*, the ethnicity of all characters, both antagonists and protagonists, was depicted as Punjabi. Some of the characters were shown as having a patriarchal and radicalized view as a result of their religious beliefs, while others were portrayed as being socially liberal. This shows Sumar's approach of linking patriarchy and misogyny with religion, instead of attributing them to a specific cultural or ethnic group. Similarly, characters in *Good Morning Karachi* were mainly from Karachi with no particular ethnic indicator. By not specifying the ethnicity of the characters in *Good*

Morning Karachi, Sumar allows the audience to focus on the issues at hand, rather than being distracted by cultural differences. This approach allows the film to have a broader appeal and resonate with a wider audience. However, in this film, the markers of social class were evident, whereby the middle or lower socioeconomic class individuals were depicted as being socially conservative in comparison to the wealthy class who were portrayed as being influenced by Western culture and having more liberal social views. This is apparently true as social class and the economic status of individuals often play a big role in shaping their beliefs, attitudes, and lifestyles. The portrayal of different social classes in *Good Morning Karachi* is in line with this reality, and it highlights the divide between the socially conservative lower classes and the more liberal elite. By doing so, Sumar sheds light on how social class affects the way people think and behave, and how it can contribute to the perpetuation of patriarchal and conservative attitudes in society.

The Ideological Implications of the Films *Idealistic Versus Realistic Presentation*

The endings of Mansoor's films were more idealistic than realistic. For example, the Sarmad and Hussain characters in *In the Name of God* experienced regret for their previous actions and underwent a transformation in their attitudes. This is a common ending in most of the moral-based stories which may not be necessarily true in the real world. The ending of a film or story can be shaped by a moral message or theme that the filmmaker wants to convey, rather than a strict representation of reality. The main character, Mary (Iman Ali), makes the decision to remain in a tribal village in Pakistan rather than returning to London, with the goal of educating the girls in the community. This follows a familiar pattern seen in Hollywood movies, where a white male superhero saves a woman of color from a man of color, a narrative that has been criticized by Spivak (1988) as a perpetuation of problematic power dynamics. In this scenario, Mary, from either London or Punjab, aids the vulnerable girls in the Pashtun tribal community, which obscures the agency of people from marginalized communities (Pashtun tribe) and reinforces power imbalances. In *Speak*, following the loss of their father, Zainab's sisters start a small food stand that, without any depiction of financial resources, evolves into a successful, high-end restaurant. This shows an ideal situation where one can start and grow a business without any investment or entrepreneurial skills. Moreover, the sisters operate their food stand on the street, disregarding the conservative norms of society where women working on the street, such as serving food, are at a greater risk of sexual harassment. This could possibly be a result of the director's cultural reaffirmation as he may have disregarded the conservative nature of Pakistani society, including Punjab.

The ideological message in Sumar's films aligns more closely with the prevailing socio-cultural norms and practices in Pakistan. In *Silent Waters*, Ayesha (Kirron Kher) becomes overwhelmed by the conservative demeanor of her son, ultimately leading to her suicide. However, her son Saleem (Aamir Ali Malik) shows little to no regret for his behavior. Saleem is depicted as eventually becoming a politician. Sumar herself witnessed his transformation in Pakistani society during

the Islamization era under General Zia's regime. *Good Morning Karachi* shows the characters of Arif (Yasir Aqueel) and Rafina (Amna Ilyas) as making their own career choices, which leads to the breakdown of their relationship. This highlights the idea of individual agency and the importance of following one's own passions and dreams, despite societal expectations and pressures. In the film, Rafina was depicted as being isolated in her professional life after breaking social barriers in order to advance her career. This is a common scenario in many societies where women who pursue careers in the entertainment industry face social disapproval and discrimination. The pressure to conform to traditional gender roles and the stigma attached to women working in the entertainment industry can make it challenging for them to pursue their career goals. Rafina's story in *Good Morning Karachi* highlights these challenges and the sacrifices women in similar circumstances have to make in order to follow their dreams.

Conservative Versus Liberal Ideologies

Mansoor represented women in a more conservative fashion in his films, with restrictions on clothing and physical contact between men and women. Mansoor, in *In the Name of God*, portrayed the relationship between the characters of Mansoor and Janie as that of a boyfriend and girlfriend, but were not depicted as engaging in physical contact, with the exception of a hug when Mansoor proposes marriage to Janie. Similarly, Mary and Dave (Alex Edwards) were portrayed in an intimate relationship in the same film, but they are not depicted as having any physical contact. This is typical of many depictions of relationships in conservative societies such as Pakistan, where physical affection is often portrayed as inappropriate or forbidden. In these societies, even the depiction of physical affection in films can be seen as controversial and may generate criticism. It is imperative to note that in *In the Name of God*, a British-Pakistani woman Mary was not depicted as hugging a British man, while Mansoor, a Pakistani man, is shown hugging an American woman. This suggests the director's gender biases, whereas being a male director, he allows greater freedom to Pakistani men than Pakistani women. Similarly, in Mansoor's *Speak*, Ayesha (Mahira Khan) and Mustafa (Atif Aslam) were in an intimate relationship, but they were not shown as having any physical contact. Another conservative value demonstrated in Mansoor's films is the depiction of alcohol consumption or the lack thereof. None of his films show characters consuming alcohol and, in fact, they are often shown declining alcohol. By avoiding the depiction of alcohol consumption and maintaining a conservative approach to clothing and physical intimacy in his films, Mansoor might have aimed to cater to the conservative cultural, religious, and ideological spheres of Pakistan. This is a common strategy used by filmmakers who want to appeal to a particular cultural or religious demographic. In the conservative sector of Pakistani society, alcohol is seen as a moral issue and its consumption is discouraged. By avoiding the depiction of alcohol, Mansoor may have tried to avoid controversy and appeal to a wider audience within Pakistan. However, it is important to note that this is just a possibility, and without further information, it is difficult to confirm the motivations behind Mansoor's artistic choices.

Compared to Mansoor, Sumar's films are less conservative. This may be due to her Western education. In *Silent Waters*, Saleem and Zubaida (Shilpa Shukla) engage in physical intimacy such as hugging, kissing, and caressing. Alcohol consumption during the wedding celebration was also spotted in the film. In *Good Morning Karachi*, physical affection including hugging, caressing, and kissing between Rafina and Arif were depicted. In the same film, the character of Rafina is depicted wearing clothing that reveals her arms, legs, and cleavage. The film also contains sexual language and characters using profanity. Additionally, the film depicts characters consuming alcohol after a fashion show party. These depictions in Sumar's films reflect her less conservative approach compared to Mansoor

Directors' Representation of Self-Professional-Identity

Some discourses are more distinct in Sumar and Mansoor films. Mansoor, a creative force in lyrics and music composition, incorporates musical elements into both of his movie projects. Mansoor demonstrated his viewpoint that music is acceptable in Islam through his film *In the Name of God*. This desire of showcasing music as permissible in Islam might have been driven by his frustration with his former protégé, Junaid Jamshed, who had declared music to be haram (forbidden) in a religious lecture. By portraying a positive representation of music in the film, Mansoor aimed to challenge the views of those who believe that music is haram in Islam. In *Speak*, one of the lead characters Mustafa was depicted as a singer, who in real life is known as Atif Aslam, a famous pop singer in Pakistan.

Sumar, a woman from a political and business class family and with a political science degree, delved into political themes in her both film. In *Silent Waters*, for example, she tackled the partition of India in 1947 and then linked the events of 1947 to the Islamization under General Zia in 1979 and the Independence Day of Pakistan. The film culminates in 2002 with a depiction of General Pervez Musharraf's referendum. In *Good Morning Karachi*, Sumar delves into the political realm of 2007 by exploring the election campaign of the former Prime Minister of Pakistan, Benazir Bhutto, and her tragic assassination. For example, in the film, a radio newscaster intermittently announces updates on Benazir Bhutto's public gatherings and later reports on her assassination. Additionally, Arif runs a political campaign for Bhutto by placing her political banners at various public spaces during the film.

Association of Religious and Gender Identities with Protagonists and Antagonists

In terms of the discourse about gender identity in Pakistan, Mansoor's and Sumar's shared some common grounds. Both filmmakers portrayed men as the oppressors of women, using religion and patriarchal cultural norms to justify their actions. These oppressors were typically the immediate male relatives of the women including their husbands or father. In *Silent Waters*, for example, Sumar depicts Ayesha's mother and sister as victims of honor killing committed by her Sikh father, thereby implying the women's victimization through the hands of their husbands and fathers. In the same film, Ayesha later became the victim of her own son, Saleem, who, after becoming religious and inclined towards Islam, made her life so

unbearable that she ultimately took her own life. In Sumar's *Good Morning Karachi*, Rafina was shown as being controlled by her fiancé, who prevented her from pursuing her career. Additionally, Fahad, who works for an advertising agency in the film, holds the belief that fashion modeling and marriage (for women) cannot get along due to the insecurity of husbands about their wives.

With regards to the intersection of religion and gender, the male characters were portrayed as having strong religious identities while the women were portrayed as having either secular or moderate religious identities. For example, in *Silent Waters*, the majority of male characters were depicted as being religious and frequently visiting the mosque, while the female characters were not shown engaging in any religious practices except for the one instance where Ayesha was teaching Quran to children. The majority of these religious male characters were portrayed as antagonists. In *Good Morning Karachi*, the mob that vandalized billboards featuring women's images was made up of men and they were chanting religious slogans. None of the female characters in the film were depicted as practicing any religion.

Mansoor's films also portrayed a similar discourse regarding the protagonists and antagonists. Women were portrayed as protagonists who were oppressed by their immediate male relatives driven by religious motivations, who acted as antagonists. Mansoor portrayed Mary in *In the Name of God*, as the victim of her father Hussain, who coerced her into marriage with Sarmad. Despite not being religious himself, Hussain used Islam to justify his actions. Sarmad, Mary's cousin, forced her into marriage and raped her (domestic rape) when he becomes religious. The protagonist characters in *In the Name of God* were women who were shown to be lower in religiosity or not religious at all, while the antagonist characters were male and were portrayed as being highly religious. In the film *Speak*, the daughters are depicted as victims of their father's actions. One such example is the character of Hakim, who was portrayed as a misogynistic man with religious beliefs and engaged in domestic violence and verbal abuse towards his wife and daughters. In the film, the male characters who served as antagonists were depicted as being highly religious, while the female characters who served as the protagonists were not shown to have any religious affiliations.

Discussion

This study examined the contemporary auteur cinema of Pakistan in terms of directors' framing of the sociopolitical climate of Pakistan in their films. This study analyzed the different ways in which two directors, Mansoor and Sumar, presented such discourses. Although both filmmakers have distinct approaches, there are similarities and differences in the way they depict the sociopolitical climate of Pakistan. Sumar mainly focuses on exceptional cases and issues that are not limited to women, whereas Mansoor specifically addresses problems that are specific to women. Despite these differences, both directors highlight the importance of education and critical examination of cultural and religious practices as a means to achieve women's empowerment.

In *In the Name of God*, director Mansoor tackled the problem of the practice of forcing women into marriages, which is a prevalent and specific social problem in Pakistan. In *Speak*, he focused on the issues pertaining to domestic violence, women's reproductive rights, and family planning. These are the concerns commonly experienced by women in conservative and underdeveloped societies, where they are often blamed for giving birth to female children, subjected to violence, and receive lesser treatment compared to their male counterparts.

While filmmaker Sumar attributed women's oppression to religion in general and Islam in particular, Mansoor placed the responsibility for the problem on the misperception of Islam by certain ethnic communities such as Pashtuns and Indians. In her films, Sumar avoided ethnic specificity by portraying individuals with differing ideologies within a similar cultural context. In *Silent Waters*, both the antagonists and protagonists belonged to the same Punjabi ethnicity, with some individuals being radicalized by fellow Punjabi men for religious and political reasons. In *Good Morning Karachi*, Sumar presented the residents of Karachi avoiding any emphasis on their ethnicity, instead contrasting those who were socially conservative and those who were socially liberal and Westernized.

In contrast, Mansoor asserted that the misperception of Islam by specific ethnic communities is accountable for the oppression of women in Pakistan. In *In the Name of God*, for example, a socially conservative cleric named Maulana Tahiri (Rasheed Naz) and his Pashtun followers were portrayed as using their interpretation of Islam to serve their patriarchal and political purposes. In comparison, Maulana Wali (Naseeruddin Shah), a cleric of Punjabi origin, was depicted as both devout and open-minded in his social views. The film also showed a Punjabi man being radicalized by a Pashtun man. Similarly, in *Speak*, the conservative and misogynistic character Hakim was portrayed as an Indian man, while his liberal and secular neighbor Akhtar Hussain was depicted as Punjabi. By presenting a clear distinction between cultural and religious motives, the film highlights that the oppression of women is not solely based on religion, but rather the patriarchal misuse of religious teachings for personal gain and control. The film also emphasizes the importance of education and the questioning of authority in interpreting religious texts, as a means to challenge patriarchal norms and promote gender equality. This discourse suggests that women's empowerment can be achieved through a critical examination of cultural and religious practices, and a rejection of oppressive interpretations of religion.

Despite their differences in discourse, Sumar and Mansoor share common ground in the way they depict women's oppression in their films. The use of the *burka* as a symbol of oppression was a common theme in at least three films analyzed, representing the restrictions and limitations placed on women by patriarchal culture and religious fundamentalism. In these films, women who wore *burka* were portrayed as being confined and controlled, and the removal of their *burka* represented their liberation and empowerment. The representation of women wearing the *burka* in these films serves to highlight the pervasive nature of patriarchal oppression in Pakistani society. For example, in Mansoor's *Speak*, the character Zainab encourages her sisters to shed their *burkas* and take control of their destinies. After doing so, they were able to start their own food stall and later turn

that into a large restaurant. Likewise, a *burka* was also visible in the Pashtun tribal women in Mansoor's *In the Name of God*, who were portrayed as oppressed by their patriarchal relatives. In *Good Morning Karachi*, the act of a woman removing her *burka* was portrayed as a symbol of empowerment.

In conclusion, the contemporary media landscape, marked by the rapid proliferation of innovative social media platforms, has elevated the role of media as both an information disseminator and an entertainment provider. This increasing dependence on media amplifies its extensive influence on society. Within this milieu, media content goes beyond its surface messages, taking on the role of a vessel for hidden meanings and concealed identities. The study's focal objective centered on an exploration of notable independent Pakistani films spanning the last two decades, seeking to unveil the distinct artistic imprints of their respective directors. The findings revealed that directors Shoaib Mansoor and Sabiha Sumar adeptly captured prevalent societal concerns, particularly those pertaining to women, employing distinctive narrative methodologies. The films of both auteurs subtly captured the echoes of their professional identities and backgrounds. Historically, research studies predominantly concentrated on the biased portrayals by Western filmmakers of Muslims, Middle Easterners, and Asians. Notably, the analysis of Pakistani films through the lens of auteur theory has been largely absent. As the media sector continues its rapid expansion, the careful examination of these auteurs' influence on their creations becomes imperative, given their content's potential to shape perceptions of societal challenges and identities through a distinct lens. It is important to note that the results of this study may not be generalizable to the entire population of filmmakers in Pakistan, as it is based on a small sample of films and filmmakers. Besides illuminating a mere fraction of the diverse meanings interwoven into these directors' films, it fundamentally underscores the broader paradigm of meaning and identity formation pertaining to cinematic craftsmanship. Collectively, these findings help us understand better how filmmakers give deep meaning and unique identity to their creations. This adds more richness and complexity to the world of movies and culture today.

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